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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
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MA. CECILIA C. DALUCAPAS, MAEd

Assistant Professor 1

University of Eastern Philippines

University Town, Catarman, Northern Samar

Region VIII, Philippines

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A Poem for Someone

A birthday a year is a gift of joy
A smile, a laugh for you to enjoy
As days turn to weeks and months to years
Blessings are yours all through the years

When days are gray and life seems gloomy
Remember your loved ones as you pray
You can't hold all things in your palm all day
But you can always cherish collected memories

At 60 I wish you all moments of bliss
Just carry life's burden with grace and ease
Hold on to faith for life to live
A hundredfold of birthdays to celebrate